

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP1 – Moving beyond pregnancy registries to enhance our understanding of disease-related pregnancy outcomes, medication use and safety of use during pregnancy

D1.4 Report on algorithms to define pregnancy, maternal morbidity and maternal, perinatal and childhood outcomes

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Abstract

Five demonstration projects were undertaken in the IMI ConcePTION study to investigate the prevalence of different maternal diseases and medication exposures during pregnancy and to enable studies of potential risks/benefits for mothers and fetuses to be conducted using national and regional data sources. To do this, several algorithms needed to be developed to identify the diseases, exposures and outcomes of interest. This report documents the 15 algorithms that were developed. For completeness, it also includes the Congenital Anomaly Algorithm that has been developed by EUROCAT (<https://doi.org/10.1002/bdr2.2314>) and in addition an appendix describes the evaluation of a set of algorithms using a disease registry compared to routine health care data .

Methods

Developing an algorithm to identify specific events or exposure in health care databases across Europe requires a literature review to be completed to identify any existing algorithms which can be adapted and any potential issues identified can be addressed and overcome. The literature review can also be useful as a benchmark for comparison of the results in different databases. Close collaboration with clinicians and patient representatives is needed to ensure that clinically relevant data are included in the algorithm. Close collaboration with the data access providers (DAPs), who have the greatest knowledge of the strengths and weaknesses of their data and the societal background of their region or country is also essential.

Once an algorithm is developed it is essential to implement it sequentially in all the databases after it is tested by one DAP. A step wise approach is more efficient as new data sources may identify issues that were not previously picked up and will enable these to be corrected.

Validation of algorithms should ideally be done by randomly selecting a set of cases and examining the individual clinical notes. However, this is not always possible if direct access to the case notes is not available, or governance restrictions prohibit clinical identification. In such circumstances validation needs to be completed by examining the prevalence in subgroups of the data that are known to vary. For example, for MS the prevalence is higher in women than men and the incidence is highest amongst women aged 30-40 years. External validation by comparing the results with other published studies or other data sources covering the same population is also recommended. In addition, expert validation by data providers and clinicians that the results are consistent with current knowledge is important.

Results

The following table provides information on the 15 algorithms developed within IMI ConcePTION to define pregnancy, maternal morbidity and maternal, perinatal and childhood outcomes. The

preexisting EUROCAT algorithm, to classify all major congenital anomalies into meaningful anomaly subgroups is included in the table, as although it was not developed in ConcePTION, its use was essential for several demonstration projects.

The table lists each algorithm together with information on how to access the protocol/statistical analysis plan which includes the code lists in each DAP, and the inclusion/exclusion criteria. Many of these algorithms are being used in studies that are currently under review and therefore it is expected that further details may be available from the lead authors for each algorithm whose contact details are provided in the table.

Preliminary work evaluating a maternal disease algorithm using a disease registry compared to routine health care data is provided in Appendix 1.

Discussion

This deliverable originally aimed to discuss the results from the validation methods used in each algorithm. However, the amount of time required to adapt the algorithms to the individual data sets was under-estimated, and the resources needed to finalize this effort were insufficient. Due to delays arising in the work packages such results are still being analysed and are not in the public domain. To overcome this, details about future publications are provided to enable interested readers to locate the relevant validation for the algorithms as soon as they are published.

Conclusion

Despite efforts to develop a comprehensive common data model, all algorithms required considerable individual tailoring to each real-world dataset. Therefore, if using these algorithms on a new data set, care should be taken that the algorithm is performing as expected.

Number	Subject	Lead Researcher (email)	Description	Protocol / Statistical Analysis Plan	Publications/Reports/abstracts	Link for Github
1	Pregnancy Outcomes	Rosa Gini (rosa.gini@ars.toscana.it)	Algorithm to identify pregnancies in health care databases with a pregnancy start and end date and the type of pregnancy end (Live birth, still birth, Spontaneous abortion, Termination, Ectopic pregnancy, Ongoing,Unknown)	SAP_task7.7_pregnancies_v5.0.docx - Google Docs		https://github.com/ARS-toscana/ConcePTIONAlgorithmPregnancies
2	Identifying indications for gabapentinoids prescriptions / dispensations	Anna-Belle Beau (ANNA-belle.beau@univ-tlse3.fr)	Algorithm to identify the indication for a gabapentinoid prescription as being neuropathic pain, epilepsy, generalized anxiety disorder and potential misuse/abuse	https://members.imi-conception.eu/Member-Area/Work-Package-1?folderid=3405&view=gridview&pageSize=10	<p>1. A first step in drug utilization and safety studies: Identifying indications for drug use in administrative data sources. A pilot study with gabapentinoids in a French healthcare data source. A contribution from the ConcePTION project. doi: 10.1002/pds.5687.</p> <p>2. Reason for gabapentinoids prescribing in pregnancy: results from four European countries A contribution from the IMI ConcePTION project (ICPE 2024)</p> <p>3. Identifying Prescribing Indication for Gabapentinoids in Pregnancy Using Electronic Health Records from Six European Countries A contribution from the IMI ConcePTION project submitted to Drug Safety</p>	https://github.com/IMI-ConcePTION/DP1-NeuropathicPain/
3	Maternal Depression	Maria Loane (ma.loane@ulster.ac.uk)/ Joanne Given (je.given@ulster.ac.uk)	Algorithm to identify maternal depression	https://members.imi-conception.eu/Portals/1/ConcePTION/Work package 1/Task 1.5/DP2-Antidepressants/DP2 Maternal depression 06 September 2024.docx?ver=2024-10-10-135657-877	Prevalence of maternal depression recorded in administrative data in five European countries: A Contribution from the ConcePTION project.	
4	Neurodevelopmental (ND) outcomes : Attention Deficit Hyperactivity disorder, ADHD; Autistic spectrum disorder, ASD; Learning disability/intellectual development disorders, ID; and delayed infant development.	Maria Loane (ma.loane@ulster.ac.uk)/Joanne Given (je.given@ulster.ac.uk)/Rebecca Bromley (rebecca.bromley@manchester.ac.uk)	Algorithm to identify children with each of the neurodevelopmental (ND) outcomes : (Attention Deficit Hyperactivity disorder, ADHD; Autistic spectrum disorder, ASD; Learning disability/intellectual development disorders, ID; and delayed infant development.	https://members.imi-conception.eu/Portals/1/ConcePTION/Work package 1/Task 1.5/DP2-Antidepressants/DP2 ND algorithm 27 Sept 24.docx?ver=2024-10-10-135648-207	<p>1.Prevalence of Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder and Autism Spectrum Disorder in administrative healthcare data in five European countries: A Contribution from the ConcePTION project</p> <p>2.Prevalence of Intellectual disability in children recorded in administrative data in five European countries: A Contribution from the ConcePTION project</p> <p>3.The impact of socio-economic status on the prevalence of delayed development in children in France and Wales: A Contribution from the ConcePTION project</p> <p>4.A European case-malformed control study assessing maternal exposure to antidepressants in the first trimester of pregnancy and risk of congenital anomalies: A contribution from the ConcePTION project (in preparation).</p>	
5	Breastfeeding	S.F.Jordan@Swansea.ac.uk	Algorithm to identify breastfeeding and risk factors preventing breastfeeding	https://members.imi-conception.eu/Portals/1/ConcePTION/Work package 1/Task 1.5/DP2-Antidepressants/BF_1.3.7_SAP_25.2.22.docx?ver=2024-10-10-145946-800	The impact of exposure to medicines and recorded diagnoses on breastfeeding in Haute-Garonne and Wales, accounting for socio-economic status: a contribution from the ConcePTION project.	
6	Multiple Sclerosis	Marie Beslay (mariebeslay@hotmail.fr)	Algorithm to identify if a person has been diagnosed with multiple sclerosis	https://members.imi-conception.eu/Member-Area/Work-Package-1?folderid=3407&view=gridview&pageSize=10/DP3_S AP algoMS_V5.docx	<p>1. Identification and prevalence assessment of multiple sclerosis in women: a multicentre database study across Europe- A contribution from the IMI2 ConcePTION project (ISPE 2023)</p> <p>2. Identifying multiple sclerosis in women of childbearing age in six European countries: A contribution to the ConcePTION project (submitted to ...)</p> <p>3. Methods of estimating Prevalence of Multiple Sclerosis in six European healthcare data sources: A contribution to the ConcePTION project (ICPE 2024)</p>	

7	Childhood Infections	Christine Damase-Michel	Algorithm to identify Childhood Infections in Health Care Databases	Protocol : https://view.officeapps.live.com/op/view.aspx?src=https%3A%2F%2Fmembers.imi-conception.eu%2FPortals%2F1%2FConcePTION%2FWork%2520package%25201%2FTask%25201.5%2FDP3-MS-SLE%2Fchildhood%2520infections.docx%3Fver%3D2024-10-14-163635-707%26timestamp%3D1728916605830&wdOrigin=BR OWSELINK		No analysis scripts completed
8	Migraine	Hedvig Nordeng (h.m.e.nordeng@farmasi.uio.no)	Algorithm to identify migraine in pregnant women and assess the type (migraine with and without aura, Complicated migraine and Migraine unspecified) and severity (mild,moderate,severe,very severe)	https://members.imi-conception.eu/Member-Area/Work-Package-1?folderId=3408&view=gridview&pageSize=10/Migraine algorithm SAP v2.0 final.docx	<i>Conference presentation:</i> Identification and characterization of migraine around pregnancy in population-based registries. Mitter VR, Lupattelli A, Bjørk MH, Nordeng HE. Poster presentation. ISPE Mid-Year Conference, April 24–25, 2023, Reykjavik, Iceland.	https://github.com/UMC-Utrecht-RWE/ConcePTION-DP4_Migraine
9	Gestational Diabetes	Hedvig Nordeng (h.m.e.nordeng@farmasi.uio.no)	Algorithm to identify gestational diabetes in pregnant women	https://members.imi-conception.eu/Member-Area/Work-Package-1?folderId=3408&view=gridview&pageSize=10Study_Protocol and SAP for Algorithms to Identify GDM and PE Version 4.2_20230619 (1)	<i>Conference presentation:</i> Algorithms to Identify Gestational Diabetes in European Healthcare Data Sources: A pilot study in Norway and Finland from the ConcePTION project. Mølgaard-Nielsen D, Mitter VR, Hoxhaj V, Navarro CA, Martikainen V, Lopez-Leon S, Maarit K Leinonen, Nordeng HME: Poster presentation. The 15th Annual NorPEN Meeting, November 22–24, 2023, Oslo, Norway. <i>Publication:</i> Identification of Gestational diabetes in European electronic healthcare data: Insights from the ConcePTION project Ditte Mølgaard-Nielsen, Vera R Mitter, Angela Lupattelli, Vjola Hoxaj, Constanza Andaur Navarro, Saeed Hayati, Sandra Lopez-Leon, Joan Morris, Susan Jordan, Maarit K Leinonen, Visa Martikainen, Marco Manfrini, Laia Barrachina-Bonet, Clara Caverro-Carbonell, Anthony Cailliet, Christine Damase-Michel, Marleen M.H.J. van Gelder, Hedvig Nordeng. <i>In preparation</i>	https://github.com/UMC-Utrecht-RWE/ConcePTION-DP4_Migraine
10	Pre-eclampsia	Hedvig Nordeng (h.m.e.nordeng@farmasi.uio.no)	Algorithm to identify preeclampsia in pregnant women	https://members.imi-conception.eu/Member-Area/Work-Package-1?folderId=3408&view=gridview&pageSize=10Study_Protocol and SAP for Algorithms to Identify GDM and PE Version 4.2_20230619 (1)	<i>Conference presentation:</i> Algorithms to Identify Preeclampsia in European Healthcare Data Sources: A pilot study in Norway and Finland from the ConcePTION project. Mitter VR, Hoxhaj V, Mølgaard-Nielsen D, Navarro CA, Martikainen V, Lopez-Leon S, Leinonen MK, Nordeng HME: Poster presentation. The 15th Annual NorPEN Meeting, November 22–24, 2023, Oslo, Norway. <i>Publication:</i> Identifying Preeclampsia in European Electronic Healthcare Data: Insights from the ConcePTION Project Sandra Lopez-Leon, Ditte Mølgaard-Nielsen, Vera R Mitter, Angela Lupattelli, Vjola Hoxaj, Constanza Andaur Navarro, Saeed Hayati, Joan Morris, Maarit K Leinonen, Visa Martikainen, Susan Jordan, Marco Manfrini, Laia Barrachina-Bonet, Clara Caverro-Carbonell, Anthony Cailliet, Christine Damase-Michel, Marleen M.H.J. van Gelder, Hedvig Nordeng. <i>In preparation</i>	https://github.com/UMC-Utrecht-RWE/ConcePTION-DP4_Migraine
11	Breast Cancer and Pregnancy Associated Breast Cancer	Maarit Leinonen (maarit.leinonen@thl.fi)	Algorithm to identify Breast Cancer and to distinguish pregnancy associated breast cancer (PABC) and non-PABC	https://members.imi-conception.eu/Member-Area/Work-Package-1?folderId=3409&view=gridview&pageSize=10/PABC_algorithm SAP_240325	1. Incidence and survival of pregnancy associated breast cancer: A contribution from the ConcePTION project piloted in Finland and Norway (ICPE 2024) 2. Incidence and Survival of Pregnancy Associated Breast Cancer: A Contribution from the IMI ConcePTION Project (NorPEN 2024)	https://github.com/UMC-Utrecht-RWE/ConcePTION-DP5
12	Breast Cancer Therapy	Maarit Leinonen (maarit.leinonen@thl.fi)	Algorithm to identify breast cancer therapies (surgery,chemotherapy, hormonal therapy and targeted therapy)	https://members.imi-conception.eu/Portals/1/ConcePTION/Work%20package%201/Task%201.5/DPS-BreastCancer/PABC%20treatment%20SAP%20final%201.1.pdf?ver=2023-03-24-103011-520&timestamp=1728916007493	1. Incidence and survival of pregnancy associated breast cancer: A contribution from the ConcePTION project piloted in Finland and Norway (ICPE 2024) 2. Incidence and Survival of Pregnancy Associated Breast Cancer: A Contribution from the IMI ConcePTION Project (NorPEN 2024)	https://github.com/UMC-Utrecht-RWE/ConcePTION-DP5

13	Small for Gestational Age	Alexis Krumme (AKrumme@ITS.JNJ.com), Ditte Mølgaard-Nielsen (DMQN@novonordisk.com)	Algorithm to identify small for gestational age using national growth charts from each country	BC pregnancy outcomes SAP 3_draftv1.4_CLEAN.pdf (imi-conception.eu)	Pregnancy and infant outcomes in gestationally-diagnosed breast cancer: A pilot study in Finland and Norway from the ConcePTION project	https://github.com/UMC-Utrecht-RWE/ConcePTION-DPS
14	Cesarean delivery	Alexis Krumme (AKrumme@ITS.JNJ.com)	Algorithm to identify Cesarean section deliveries	BC pregnancy outcomes SAP 3_draftv1.4_CLEAN.pdf (imi-conception.eu)	<u>Pregnancy and infant outcomes in gestationally-diagnosed breast cancer: A pilot study in Finland and Norway from the ConcePTION project</u>	https://github.com/UMC-Utrecht-RWE/ConcePTION-DPS
15	Pre-term birth	Anja Geldhof (ageldho1@its.jnj.com), Carla Morris	Algorithm to identify pre-term births	Study Protocol and SAP for algorithms to identify Preterm Birth in ConcePTION population-based data sources (Task 1.3.1) June 2022		No analysis scripts completed
16	Major Congenital Malformations	Helen Dolk (h.dolk@ulster.ac.uk)	Algorithm to classify major congenital anomalies into meaningful anomaly subgroups.	1. https://view.officeapps.live.com/op/view.aspx?src=https%3A%2F%2Fmembers.imi-conception.eu%2FPortals%2F1%2FConcePTION%2FWork%2520package%25201%2FTask%25201.5%2FDP3-MS-SLE%2FDP3_SAP_Euromedicat_MS.docx%3Fver%3D2023-03-14-101919-330%26timestamp%3D1728914621498&wdOrigin=BROWSELINK	1. EUROCAT Guide 1.4 (https://eu-rd-platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/eurocat/data-collection/guidelines-for-data-registration_en#inline-nav-3) 2. Specific congenital anomalies associated with maternal Multiple Sclerosis: A ConcePTION European case-malformed control study (ICPE 2024) 3. Gabapentinoids exposure in early pregnancy and risk of congenital anomalies : a ConcePTION European case-malformed control study (SFPT 2024) 4. Gabapentinoids exposure in early pregnancy and risk of congenital anomalies: a ConcePTION European case-malformed control study (ICPE 2024)	

Appendix 1

Evaluating MS algorithms using data from the UK MS Register and the Healthcare Databank in Wales

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Abstract

Multiple sclerosis (MS) may be managed with disease modifying treatment (DMT). As with many long-term pharmacotherapies for serious but rare conditions, the impact of these DMTs on pregnancy, the infant and breastfeeding is largely unexplored, not least due to the difficulties of including pregnant women in clinical trials. Accordingly, pharmacovigilance depends on observation studies. Equipose persists regarding use of population-based routine healthcare databanks *versus* disease registers collecting data from volunteers.

The aims of this sub-study were to 1) compare data from the online UK MS register (UKMSR) with that in the population databank, the secure anonymised information linkage (SAIL), in Wales, and 2) to explore algorithms for identification of MS in the databank.

Participants and setting

Records of women in Wales aged 15-55 were extracted from the population databank (SAIL) 1998-2020 and from UKMSR from inception (2011) to 2020.

Methods

Women from the UKMSR were linked with their records in the population databank via their ID numbers. Read codes (v2), ICD10 codes and ATC codes for DMTs were identified in SAIL. Numbers linked and identified by each of 10 algorithms were described.

Results

403 women in the UKMSR were identified in the population databank (SAIL); of these, 56 (16%) had no MS diagnosis in SAIL. Depending on algorithm used, SAIL identified up to 1597 women with MS. More cases of MS were identified when primary and secondary care data were combined, and when number of recorded events was reduced from 3 to 2. Many women prescribed DMTs had no MS diagnoses, largely because other indications for these medicines are common. Very few prescriptions were recorded in UKMSR, for example mycophenolate mofetil was prescribed to 763 women in SAIL, but there were no records of use in UKMSR.

Fewer than 65 pregnancies were identified in UKMSR, whereas 1287 pregnancies were recorded in SAIL following an MS diagnosis or DMT prescription. UKMSR held no information on pregnancy outcomes or breastfeeding.

Implications

UKMSR offered very little information not available in SAIL. The low number of pregnancies reported and the paucity of information available on DMT indicates that this voluntary register cannot be adapted to report on pharmacovigilance for pregnant and breastfeeding women; it was not designed for this.

List of abbreviations

ATC, anatomical therapeutic chemical code

CARIS, congenital anomalies register for Wales

DMT disease modifying treatment

GP, general medical practitioner, primary care physician

IBD, irritable bowel disease

ICD, international classification of disease

im, intramuscular

iv, intravenous

MS, multiple sclerosis

OPDW, out patient dataset for Wales

PEDW, patient episode database for Wales, hospital admissions

SAIL, secure anonymised information linkage, the Wales health and social care databank

Sc, subcutaneous

UKMSR, UK MS register

WLGP, Welsh Longitudinal general practice database

Background

Women with multiple sclerosis (MS) receive diagnoses and medicines from different sources including inpatient stays, outpatient contacts, primary care prescriptions, 'over the counter' from pharmacies, general sale, and internet purchases. One aspect of DP3 and task 1.6 is to investigate the accuracy of the data relating to MS in health care databases and congenital anomaly registries. This includes comparing the data in the volunteer MS register with that in the Wales whole-population health service databank, the secure anonymised information linkage (SAIL). We hypothesise that all people in the UKMS register (UKMSR) living in Wales will be linked to a primary care record in the Wales databank (SAIL), but many people with MS and identifiable in the SAIL databank will not volunteer to register with UKMSR, due to personal choice, lack of internet connection or simply being unaware of the register.

Introduction

Multiple Sclerosis usually has a remitting-relapsing natural history that includes sporadic and unpredictable episodes that may be severely disabling. As the condition progresses, comorbidities often emerge, including seizures, depression, and vision loss, necessitating concomitant prescribing. Women with MS experiencing disease relapses or flares are treated with the aim of either preventing new disease relapses or controlling the relapse. Disease modifying treatments (DMTs) aimed at preventing relapses are important at all times, including during pregnancy, as relapses increase disease progression. Pregnancy is characterised by MS remission, but relapse is common in the first trimester *post-partum* (Hellwig et al 2021, Modrego et al 2021). This may be mitigated by exclusive breastfeeding (Langer-Gould et al 2020).

The prevalence rate of MS in Wales is reported as 168 / 100,000 (0.168%) (all ages, both sexes) (Mackenzie et al 2014, Balbuena et al 2016), indicating that ~5,000 people in Wales are currently experiencing MS. Pregnancy rates in MS appear comparable with the general population [in the USA] at ~9% for 2006-15, but outcomes are generally less favourable (Houtchens et al 2018). MS either does not affect fertility or has a small effect, and the proportion of women using assisted reproductive technology is comparable with that of the general population (Sadovnick et al 2021).

Systematic reviews indicate that DMTs reduce relapse rates when compared with placebo over a 2 year period, but some medicines are more effective than others, and compliance varies with medicine (Li et al 2020, Liu et al 2021). Evidence for disability progression is less certain (Fogarty et al 2016). Some clinicians are reluctant to prescribe DMTs, due to the uncertain risks of severe ADRs (Cameron et al 2019), such as PML (progressive multifocal leukoencephalopathy) (Sriwastava et al 2021). Some DMTs (e.g. interferons) are regarded as safe during pregnancy, based on limited data in humans, but concerns remain regarding

analgesia (e.g. gabapentin), antiepileptics, and muscle relaxants (e.g. baclofen, cannabis extract) (BNF 2023). Some authorities advise against some DMTs during pregnancy, as there is little information available (Pregnancy and MS 2019).

MS treatment and progression is recorded in health service databases and voluntary MS registries, 20 of which are in Europe, including the UK MS register (UKMSR) based in Swansea (Flachenecker et al 2014). Women who volunteer to join the UK register are identifiable in routine healthcare databases, including the Wales secure anonymised information linkage (SAIL) databank <https://saildatabank.com/>, and the Wales congenital anomaly register (CARIS) <https://phw.nhs.wales/services-and-teams/caris/>.

UKMSR

The online UKMSR was commissioned by the MS society of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, and is stored securely in Swansea University (Ford et al 2012). Since 2011, it has been using serial validated questionnaires to capture data from people over 18 with MS who volunteer to participate via a purpose-built internet portal (Middleton et al 2018), promoted in NHS neurology clinics (Ford et al 2012). In 2018, there were 11,021 unique participants; since some 5% of the UK population live in Wales, we should expect ~500 people in UKMSR to live in Wales. Mean age at entry to the register is 52 years (SD 11.9), and mean age at diagnosis is 37.4 years (SD 37.4), rather younger than reported in the whole population (Mackenzie et al 2014). Self-reported information was collected quarterly (Middleton et al 2018), but, since 2018, has been collected every 6 months (MS society 2023). A proportion of the data is verified by NHS centres (Middleton et al 2018, personal communication). 270 variables available are listed in an excel file (available from the authors as supplementary information), and a minimal dataset is available in appendix B in Middleton et al (2018). Data on patient reported outcome measures are also collected. Participants may consent to their data being linked with electronic clinical data: however, there are some discrepancies e.g. in diagnosis (17%), year of diagnosis (35%), and agreement between patients and clinicians regarding symptoms of disability and disease progression is moderate to poor (weighted kappa ranging from 0.26 for visual symptoms to 0.59 for bowel/bladder symptoms) (Leddy et al 2012). Wales and Northern Ireland are over-represented, due to strong links with treatment centres. Volunteer selection bias is acknowledged as a feature of recruited cohorts (Middleton et al 2018). Engaging with the internet to complete relatively lengthy questionnaires (~30 minutes every 6 months) militates against engagement by people who are seriously ill or busy; professionals are over-represented in UKMSR, whilst those with 'elementary occupations' are under-represented (Ford et al 2012).

Aims

- Firstly, to investigate the concordance between data recorded in UKMSR and SAIL in terms of diagnoses and prescriptions for MS.
- Secondly to review algorithms for the identification of MS within SAIL, and, by implication, other electronic health service records.

Objectives

To determine the:

1. Linkage completeness for women from the MS register in SAIL
2. Accuracy of MS diagnoses in SAIL including availability of measures of disease severity, when compared with the MS register, by reviewing algorithms
3. Accuracy and completeness of medicine codes in SAIL and CARIS, when compared with the MS register
4. Pregnancy reporting in UKMSR, and hence utilisation of MS medications before and during pregnancy and *post-partum*

Setting and Participants

We interrogated the SAIL databank to identify women of childbearing age (15 to 55) in Wales between 1998 and 2020. Within this SAIL-based cohort, we identified women with MS by interrogating the primary care (general practice /GP, WLGP), hospital admissions (PEDW) and hospital outpatients (OPDW) databases using diagnostic or prescription codes.

SAIL links almost all (>99%) mother-infant dyads [Health Data Research Innovation Gateway \(healthdatagateway.org\)](https://healthdatagateway.org), and children to their health records. Hospital records are linked to 98.9% of children (Urhoj et al 2022), and 99% of children with major anomalies registered in EUROCAT are linked to vital statistics (Loane et al 2021). Some 20% more children are recorded as having a major congenital anomaly in the EUROCAT congenital anomaly register (CARIS) than in the concurrent hospital data (Bakker et al 2023).

Women resident in Wales registered with UKMSR were linked with their SAIL records.

Methods

This was a database linkage sub-study, aiming to compare the data available in the UK MS register with data in SAIL. The UKMSR opened in 2011, but participants were, in the main, resident in Wales before that date. The analyses below were derived from the DP3 analysis plan v5. Analyses were undertaken stepwise.

Method for each Objective

1. Linkage

We calculated the number of women aged 15 to 55 during the period 1998 to 2020, identified with MS from SAIL (GP register, PEDW, OPDW) using a single entry of either ICD10 code G35 or any Read code listed in Table 1 and in UKMSR (UKMS register) concomitantly. Women who had left the SAIL databank through emigration or death were not included.

2. Algorithms for Diagnoses

Algorithms, from project leads in St. George’s hospital, to Identify people in SAIL with MS were combinations of ICD10, Read, and ATC codes:

- 1) ICD10 code : G35 and /or
- 2) READ codes in table 1 below (from <https://conceptlibrary.saildatabank.com/account/login/>)

Table 1 : READ Codes v2 concerning Multiple Sclerosis

Code	Description
666A.	Multiple sclerosis review
666B.	Multiple sclerosis multidisciplinary review
8Cc0.	Management of multiple sclerosis in onset phase
8Cc1.	Management of multiple sclerosis in early disease phase
8Cc2.	Management of multiple sclerosis in stable disability phase
8Cc4.	Management of multiple sclerosis in palliative phase
8CS1.	Multiple sclerosis care plan agreed
8IAb.	Multiple sclerosis review declined
9kG..	Spec serv for pat with multiple sclerosis - enh serv admin
9mD0.	Multiple sclerosis monitoring first letter
9mD1.	Multiple sclerosis monitoring second letter
9mD..	Multiple sclerosis monitoring administration
F200.	Multiple sclerosis of the brain stem
F201.	Multiple sclerosis of the spinal cord
F202.	Generalised multiple sclerosis
F203.	Exacerbation of multiple sclerosis
F204.	Benign multiple sclerosis
F206.	Primary progressive multiple sclerosis
F207.	Relapsing and remitting multiple sclerosis
F208.	Secondary progressive multiple sclerosis
F20..	Multiple sclerosis
F20z.	Multiple sclerosis NOS

And / Or

- 3) DMT prescriptions : Alemtuzumab (ATC: L04AA34), Dimethyl fumarate (ATC: N07XX09), Fingolimod (ATC: L04AA27), Glatiramer acetate (ATC: L03AX13), Interferon beta-1a (ATC: L03AB07), Interferon beta-1b (ATC: L03AB08), Mitoxantrone (ATC: L01DB07), Natalizumab (ATC: L04AA23), Peginterferon beta-1a (ATC: L03AB13), Rituximab (ATC:

L01XC02), Teriflunomide (ATC: L04AA31), Methotrexate (ATC: L04AX03). Many of these prescriptions are initiated by specialists in secondary or tertiary care, and continuation in primary care depends on primary care prescribing, as advised by consultants. Oral, subcutaneous (sc) and intramuscular (im) administration is usually undertaken in primary care. Some medicines are only available by intravenous (iv) administration, and these are almost exclusively administered in hospitals; however, primary care physicians usually record use of the medicines, but generally as a single record. (Template 3 has details.)

These algorithms used PEDW and WLGP (primary care) data, omitting OPDW (table 2).

Table 2 : Algorithms to identify MS patients

Algo. No.	Inpatient Diagnoses * > 28 days apart	Primary care Diagnoses * > 28 days apart	Inpatient <i>or</i> primary care Diagnoses* > 28 days apart	DMT prescriptions	Description
MS1	≥2				MS1- Number of women with MS from PEDW table with 2 and more MS event at least 28 days apart
MS2	≥3				MS2- Number of women with MS from PEDW table with 3 or more MS event at least 28 days apart
MS3		≥2			MS3- Number of women with MS from WLGP with 2 and more MS event at least 28 days apart
MS4		≥3			MS4- Number of women with MS from WLGP with 3 or more MS event at least 28 days apart
MS5			≥2		MS5- Number of women with MS either from PEDW or WLGP with 2 or more MS events at least 28 days apart
MS6			≥3		MS6- Number of women with MS either from PEDW or WLGP with 3 or more MS events at least 28 days apart
MS7				≥3	MS7- Number of women with any of the DMT prescription 3 or more times at least 28 days apart
MS8			≥1	≥2	MS8- Number of women with MS either from PEDW or WLGP with 1 or more MS event(s) at least 28 days apart AND/OR with any of the DMT prescription 2 or more times at least 28 days apart
MS9			≥2	≥1	MS9- Number of women with MS either from PEDW or WLGP with 2 or more MS events at least 28 days apart AND/OR with any DMT prescription 1 or more times at least 28 days apart
MS10			≥3	≥1	MS10- Number of women with MS either from PEDW or WLGP with 3 or more MS events at least 28 days apart AND/OR with any DMT prescription 1 or more times at least 28 days apart

*Diagnoses include ICD10 G35 and any of the READ codes in table 1. Outpatients were identified from WLGP using Read codes provided in table 1. DMT prescriptions were identified from WLGP using the medication list above. Some of these medicines have indications other than MS.

Analyses were restricted by incompatibility of data available: the Expanded Disability Status Score is reported in the UKMSR, but not in SAIL; UKMSR does not hold data on confounders such as co-prescriptions. We explored availability of 'type of MS'.

3. Medicines codes

Comparing reported use of DMT in SAIL and UKMSR

ATC codes were obtained for all DMTs, and converted to the Read V2 codes used to interrogate the SAIL databank's primary care database (WLGP). Some DMTs explored, as listed in Template 3, are not indicated for MS in the UK (BNF NICE 2023). Read / ATC codes were checked for their presence in WLGP in March 2021. For each DMT, prescriptions in WLGP were compared with reported use in UKMSR. Presence of at least one MS Read code as listed in Table 1 was used to identify women with MS in WLGP. Drug utilisation will be explored in DP1.3.

4. Pregnancy

We explored strategies to identify pregnancies in both databases, using National Community Child Health Database (NCCHD) and UKMSR. SAIL holds the NCCHD, which reports all legal live and stillbirths to residents of Wales, as reported to the Office of National Statistics (ONS), with gestation. Women in UKMSR with recorded pregnancies in NCCHD and WLGP or PEDW data were identified 1998-2020. In SAIL, the number of women with MS was calculated with 4 strategies: primary care (WLGP) as ATC codes (Table 3) or Read code F20 (Table 1), hospital admissions (PEDW), and outpatients (OPDW) as ICD 10 code 35. The 4 strategies were then combined. We then linked these women to NCCHD to ascertain whether they had given birth at any time, before and after their MS diagnosis. The number of women with MS with no recorded pregnancies was then calculated.

Safety of medicines in pregnancy will be reported in DP1.3. We explored the possibility of linking UKMSR with the congenital anomaly database (CARIS). We would expect any children with congenital anomalies (CA) born to women with MS to be included in CARIS and EUROCAT. CARIS has been linked into SAIL; therefore, all known pregnancies to women with MS can be matched in CARIS. CARIS usually holds information on maternal diagnoses and medicines taken in the first trimester. This can be compared with the data from the UKMS register and the SAIL Databank, as previously (de Jonge et al 2015).

Results

From the population of Wales 1998-2020, 917,138 women of childbearing age were identified as remaining in Wales in 2020. With a population prevalence of 168/100,000, we should expect ~1540 of these women to be diagnosed with MS.

1. Completeness of Linkage of UKMSR register (UKMSR) and SAIL Databank and proportion of cases covered in both databases

Both databases had a user ID field. UKMSR held data on 403 women of childbearing age. A substantial minority of women in UKMSR (56, 16.14%) were not identified with MS in SAIL. Linkage was lowest for women 35-44, and 2010-2014. Template 1 displays the number of women aged 15 to 55 during the period 1998 to 2020, identified in UKMSR and SAIL (GP register, PEDW, OPDW) using at least one entry of either ICD10 code G35 or any Read code listed in Table 1.

Template 1: MS Identification Completeness

- a- Women in UKMSR and also present in SAIL with any MS diagnosis (Read or ICHD10 code)
- b- Women in UKMSR but not present in SAIL with any Read or ICD10 code for MS

	Women in UKMSR (total)	Women in SAIL with at least 1 MS diagnosis		Percentage in SAIL without MS diagnosis (b/(a+b))
		Yes (a)	No (b)	
All women aged under 55 in UKMSR (403)		347	56	16.14 %
Age entering UKMSR				
	15-34 (172)	147	25	17.01 %
	35-44 (151)	135	16	11.85 %
	45-55 (80)	65	15	23.08 %
Total	403	347	56	16.14%
Year of earliest data in UKMSR				
	1998-2004 (85)	76	9	11.84 %
	2005-2009 (105)	90	15	16.67 %
	2010-2014 (111)	102	9	8.82 %
	2015-2020 (102)	79	23	29.11 %
Total	403	347	56	16.14%

UKMSR coverage starts at age 18. Any women aged 15-18 in SAIL with MS would not appear in UKMSR until age 18, but data from age 15 would be available in SAIL.

On exploration, outpatient data (OPDW):

- Were too sparse;
- Often had no diagnosis attached;
- Sometimes indicated a referral for a putative diagnosis rather than a confirmed diagnosis;
- Did not always signify outpatient attendance.

Therefore, they were not used in the algorithms.

2. Algorithms for MS Diagnosis in the SAIL Databank

Template 2. MS Diagnoses in SAIL databank 1998-2020: numbers of women

Algorithm Number	1. In UKMSR and in SAIL with MS using this algorithm	2. In UKMSR & SAIL but without MS diagnosis recorded using this algorithm 1998-2020	3. In SAIL with MS with this algorithm but not in UKMSR	SAIL total (columns 1 + 3)	Algorithm description as in table 2 in methods
MS1	204	199	994	1198	MS1- Number of women with MS from PEDW table with 2 and more MS events at least 28 days apart
MS2	151	252	742	893	MS2- Number of women with MS from PEDW table with 3 or more MS events at least 28 days apart
MS3	193	210	832	1025	MS3- Number of women with MS from WLGP with 2 and more MS events at least 28 days apart
MS4	117	286	493	617	MS4- Number of women with MS from WLGP with 3 or more MS events at least 28 days apart
MS5	270	133	1327	1597	MS5- Number of women with MS either from PEDW or WLGP with 2 and more MS events at least 28 days apart
MS6	203	200	956	1159	MS6- Number of women with MS either from PEDW or WLGP with 3 and more MS events at least 28 days apart
MS7	5	398	3159	3164	MS7- Number of women with any of the DMT prescriptions 3 or more times at least 28 days apart
MS8	344	59	5436	5780	MS8- Number of women with MS either from PEDW or WLGP with 1 or more MS event(s) at least 28 days apart AND/OR (added to those) with any of the DMT prescriptions 2 or more times at least 28 days apart
MS9	291	112	5580	5871	MS9- Number of women with MS either from PEDW or WLGP with 2 or more MS events at least 28 days apart AND/OR (added to those) with any of the DMT prescriptions 1 or more times at least 28 days apart
MS10	243	160	5256	5499	MS10- Number of women with MS either from PEDW or WLGP with 3 or more MS events at least 28 days apart And/OR (added to those) with any of the DMT prescriptions 1 or more times at least 28 days apart

Algorithms did not identify all women in UKMSR. Number of women from UKMSR is 403 for all algorithms (rows). Estimate for women with MS in SAIL from population prevalence is ~1540. OPDW was not used in these algorithms.

We failed to identify any reports of type of MS in UKMSR. In general, data coverage improved in later years. Details of timeframes are in Supplementary table 2.

3. Accuracy of medication usage records in SAIL and UKMS Register

Prescription records were analysed for ATC codes of all DMT /DMARDS selected by project leads to identify co-occurrence in the two databases 1998-2020. Women in the GP data receiving DMT may or may not have received an MS diagnosis: for example, azathioprine is prescribed for other relatively common conditions, such as IBD and rheumatoid arthritis (Template 3).

Identification of medicines

Five medications from the MS list were not identified in either primary care data or UKMSR in March 2021: cladribine, glatiramer, ocrelizumab, siponimod, ozanimod. Checks against alternative public domain databases are reported in Table 3. In 2021, ozanimod had no UK data sheet. The other 4 were for specialist use or specialist initiation. There were no records of primary care prescribing for any of these in 2021 or September 2020. <https://nwssp.nhs.wales/ourservices/primary-care-services/general-information/data-and-publications/general-practice-prescribing-data-extract/> and hospital data 2021 did not record any of these medicines <https://nwssp.nhs.wales/ourservices/primary-care-services/general-information/data-and-publications/hospital-prescribing-data-extract/> All medicines had limited indications and high costs.

Ocrelizumab and glatiramer appeared in the Health Boards' formularies in 2021. Cladribine, glatiramer, ocrelizumab have limited indications. We do not know if adverse effects or costs were considerations.

Table 3 Medicines not identified

Medicine			
Ozanimod	Not listed in bnf no.80,	Oral administration for MS (relapsing remitting) & ulcerative colitis.	Data sheet available from 3.2.23. Zeposia 0.23 mg hard capsules - Summary of Product Characteristics (SmPC) - (emc) (medicines.org.uk)
Siponimod	Authorised January 2021, Did not appear in the data in August 2021.	Oral administration, initiated by specialist. Costs for hospitals: £1643 for 28 2 mg tablets (BNF 80).	Genotyping for CYP2C9 needed before administration Mayzent 2 mg film-coated tablets - Summary of Product Characteristics (SmPC) - (emc) (medicines.org.uk) . Probably too recently authorised to be prescribed in primary care at the time of data search. Authorised January 2020 (SmPC), but rejected by NICE June 2020, and approved by NICE November 2020 Wales & England. https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ta656 & https://mstrust.org.uk/news/siponimod-mayzent-approved-active-secondary-progressive-ms-england-and-wales

Cladribine	Authorised 1995	Specialist use only. Oral administration for MS & leukaemia. 6 tablets cost £12,283. Injections cost £165, hospital only (bnf 80).	NICE approval 2019 https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ta616/resources/cladribine-for-treating-relapsingremitting-multiple-sclerosis-pdf-82608960149701 Not found on formulary https://gov.wales/sites/default/files/publications/2020-02/the-new-treatment-fund-health-board-formulary-status-2019.pdf Concerns about increased risks of cancer have not been upheld. (Pakpoor et al 2015) BNF 80 gives warnings of progressive multifocal encephalopathy.
Glatiramer	Authorised April 2003 There is no SMC for glatiramer, only the acetate.	sc injections initiated by specialists. ¹² prefilled syringes cost >£500 (bnf 80)	Glatiramer acetate was identified. Approved by NICE 2018: Glatiramer acetate is recommended as an option for treating multiple sclerosis, only if: • the person has relapsing–remitting multiple sclerosis and • the company provides it according to the commercial arrangement. https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ta527/resources/beta-interferons-and-glatiramer-acetate-for-treating-multiple-sclerosis-pdf-82606845513157 Appears to be 'on formulary for AWTTC 2018 https://gov.wales/sites/default/files/publications/2020-02/the-new-treatment-fund-health-board-formulary-status-2018.pdf
Ocrelizumab	Authorised 2018	Iv injections, initiated by specialists. 30mg for infusion costs £4,790 (bnf no.80).	NICE 2018 approval is limited. Ocrelizumab is recommended as an option for treating relapsing–remitting multiple sclerosis in adults with active disease defined by clinical or imaging features, only if: alemtuzumab is contraindicated or otherwise unsuitable and the company provides ocrelizumab according to the commercial arrangement. https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ta533/resources/ocrelizumab-for-treating-relapsingremitting-multiple-sclerosis-pdf-82606899260869 Appears to be 'on formulary for AWTTC 2018 https://gov.wales/sites/default/files/publications/2020-02/the-new-treatment-fund-health-board-formulary-status-2018.pdf

Costs listed relate to time of analysis, 2021.

6619 women 15-55 had at least 1 MS code and/or a DMT prescription 1998-2020. (Using a single MS code gave a higher number than in Template 2, MS9, 5871.) Altogether, 4794 prescribing episodes (1 or more prescriptions of a medicine) were recorded in SAIL, and <41 in UKMSR (template 3). A small number of women were prescribed >1 DMT. More women were prescribed DMT than had MS. It may be possible to infer that those prescribed a medicine with indications other than MS and not on the MS register had another indication for the prescription. Medicines recorded in UKMSR and not in SAIL likely emanated from hospital prescribing, but there were no more than 41 cases for all medicines combined.

Some DMTs in our algorithm are not indicated for MS, according to the BNF (NICE 2023) e.g. leflunomide, mitoxantrone, rituximab, and mycophenolate mofetil, but were prescribed to several hundred women with MS. Dual diagnosis cannot be excluded.

Intravenous medicines e.g. alemtuzumab, natalizumab, are usually prescribed and administered in hospitals, sometimes without overnight stays, and are often noted in GP records. However, GP recording is often as a single data entry, rather than every clinic visit.

Template 3 : Comparison of medicines in UKMSR and SAIL, women 15-55, 1998-2020

Medication ATC Code	Number of women ever taken or prescribed specified medication				Other indications (in BNF 2023) include:	Route of administration
	Recorded* in UKMSR AND SAIL	Recorded in UKMSR NOT recorded in SAIL	Recorded in SAIL with diagnosis of MS** NOT recorded in UKMSR	Not recorded in SAIL or UKMSR: women with diagnosis of MS**		
Alemtuzumab ATC: L04AA34	<5	<10	29	<6590	Unlicensed in oncology, transplants	Iv
Azathioprine ATC:L04AX01	0	0	2882	3737	IBD, rheumatoid, transplants, SLE, auto-immune disease, etc	Oral or iv
Cladribine ATC:L04A A40	0	<5	0	<6619	CLL, leukaemia	Oral, sc or iv
Daclizumab ATC:L04AC01	0	0	0	6619		oral
Dimethyl fumarate/ Tecfidera ATC:N07XX09	0	0	98	6521	-	Oral
Fingolimod ATC:L04AA27	<5	<5	39	<6580	-	Oral
Glatiramer ATC:L04A A07	0	0	0	6619		No information
Glatiramer acetate/Copaxone ATC:L03AX13	0	0	52	6567	-	Sc
Interferon beta-1a ATC:L03A B07	0	0	23	6596	Single demyelinating events	sc or im
Interferon beta-2a ATC:L03A B08	0	0	<5	<6619	Single demyelinating events	No information
Leflunomide ATC:L04A A13	0	0	776	5843	Rheumatoid, psoriatic arthritis, not MS	Oral

Mitoxantrone ATC:L01DB07	0	0	<5	<6619	Ca breast, leukaemia, not MS	Iv
Mycophenolate mofetil ATC:L04A A06	0	0	763	5856	Transplants, not MS	Oral or iv
Natalizumab ATC:L04AA23	<5	<15	43	<6576	-	Iv
Ocrelizumab ATC:L04AA36	0	6	0	6613	-	Iv
peginterferon beta-1a ATC:L03AB13	0	0	17	6602	-	Sc
Rituximab ATC:L01XC02	0	0	54	6565	Non- Hodgkin's, pemphigus, not MS	Iv or sc
Teriflunomide ATC:L04AA31	<5	0	18	<6601	-	Oral
Ofatumumab ATC:L01XC10	0	0	0	6619		Sc
Siponimod ATC:L04AA42	0	0	0	6619		Oral
Ozanimod ATC:L04AA38	0	0	0	6619		oral

*UKMSR reports women's records of medicines used. DMT medicines are prescription only. SAIL's prescription records do not indicate adherence to DMT. SAIL holds records on primary care prescribing only.

** 'with MS' indicates any MS related read code or DMT code in WLGP, the primary care database.

Women may have been using >1 medicine.

Medicines data from the 2 sources are not well matched. UKMS gives women's voluntary reports of medicines used. SAIL reports prescriptions issued in primary care. It is possible that some prescriptions were not used, but most women with medicines in SAIL, but not in UKMSR, would have had alternative diagnoses, rather than being non-adherent. It is also possible that UKMS includes medicines prescribed in secondary or tertiary care, and not reported to the primary care team (alemtuzumab, fingolimod, ocrelizumab). UKMSR includes only names of medicines used, without ATC codes; therefore, there was not always sufficient detail to match with SAIL records e.g. 'Interferon' recorded in UKMSR could be interpreted as interferon 1a, 2a and peginterferon in SAIL records, and we could not be certain of the match. For some medicines, adding UKMS medicines data offers a more complete picture of exposure than using the GP data alone e.g. fingolimod. For others, there is no difference e.g. Glariramer, dimethyl fumarate.

We found almost no information in UKMSR to inform us regarding completeness and accuracy of information on dose and timing. Due to the low numbers identified, we did not proceed to explore recording of adjunct and all other medicines, including medicines for epilepsy, pain and muscle relaxation. Timing of medicines' use was compared for women **with the four medicines reported in**

both SAIL and UKMSR (Column 2 in template 3, above), where there were >5 users of the medicine. However, no medicine had >4 users in either UKMSR or SAIL. Most prescriptions appear later in SAIL than on the UKMS register, as prescriptions are initiated in secondary or tertiary care, then transferred to primary care.

Template 4 : Comparison of timing of medicines use in UKMSR and SAIL

Medicine (ATC Code)	Number of People with				Total users recorded in both UKMSR & SAIL
	First prescription in UKMSR	First prescription in SAIL	First prescription in SAIL	First prescription in UKMSR	
	Prescription in SAIL during same year	Prescription in SAIL after 1 year	Prescription in UKMSR during same year	Prescription in UKMSR after 1 year	
Teriflunomide	<5	0	<5	0	<5
Alemtuzumab (ATC: L04AA34)	0	<5	0	0	<5
Fingolimod	<5	<5	0	0	<5
Natalizumab	0	<5	0	0	<5

4. Pregnancy reporting in SAIL Databank and UK MS Register

In UKMSR we identified one field for pregnancy: “Is the participant currently pregnant” with a date stamp attached. No variables indicated the outcome of the pregnancy. There were no data on breastfeeding. Our governance restrictions on reporting miscarriages prohibited further exploration. We were unable to assess the mother/infant linkage for women in UKMSR, but this is reported for the general population as 99.98% complete, with some early neonatal deaths pre-2003 unmatched due to absence of NHS numbers [Health Data Research Innovation Gateway \(healthdatagateway.org\)](http://healthdatagateway.org).

Using ATC codes, primary and secondary care data (PEDW, OPDW, WLGP) identified 6619 women with MS (1 or more diagnosis) in SAIL. Of these, 3819 (57.7%) women had given birth, and 2800 (42.3%) had not. More pregnancies (3722, 43.8% of women) occurred before the diagnosis (or prescription) than after (1287, 19.4% women). Some women gave birth before and after the diagnosis (Template 5).

Template 5 Women whose records indicate MS in any SAIL database*, with and without pregnancy (n=6619)

Timing of pregnancy	Number of women with a pregnancy
Women in WLGP/PEDW/OPDW had pregnancy after MS diagnosis***	1287 19.44% of women in SAIL had at least one pregnancy after MS diagnosis (1998-2020)
Women in WLGP/PEDW/OPDW had pregnancy before MS diagnosis***	2897 43.77% of women in SAIL had at least one pregnancy

	before MS diagnosis (1998-2020)
Women in WLGP/PEDW/OPDW with MS diagnosis – pregnancy ever ***	3819 57.70% of women in SAIL diagnosed with MS (1998-2020) had at least one pregnancy recorded (ever)
Women in WLGP/PEDW/OPDW with MS diagnosis – pregnancy never 1998-2020	2800 42.30% of women in SAIL diagnosed with MS had no recorded pregnancies

*WLGP, (Primary care database – Welsh Longitudinal general practice database – GP register) + PEDW, (hospital admissions – patient episodes) + OPDW (Out patient episodes)

*** These counts are irrespective of birth orders: women can be counted twice if they had pregnancy before and after MS

Of the 403 women in UKMSR <292 were recorded in the child health database (NCCHD) as having given birth 1998-2020; <65 of these had given birth since 2011, the start date of UKMSR. Of these, <25 had used DMT, at any time, 60 had a GP diagnosis of MS, and 50 had a hospital admission for MS. (Appendix 2)

Medicine safety reporting and the CARIS Database

We did not link the MSUKR with CARIS. As above, UKMSR appears to hold data on only ~30% of women with MS, and has no useable information on the dates of birth of their children. We identified <65 births to women on UKMSR between 2011 and 2020. The low numbers of women, the much lower numbers exposed to any single medicine, and our reporting restrictions on numbers <5, left us unable to explore adverse perinatal outcomes. Analyses would be likely to yield very wide confidence intervals and generate numbers <5, due to the low proportion of births with measured adverse outcomes (Supplementary Table 3). Adverse perinatal events will be analysed in the safety study of DP1.3, where data will be available from several European countries.

Discussion

UKMSR held data on 403 women of childbearing age. Given a population MS prevalence of 168/ 100,000 in Wales (Mackenzie et al 2014, Balbuena et al 2016), and 917,138 women 15-55 identified in SAIL, we should expect SAIL, the population databank, to identify some 1,540 people with MS; comparison with the general population does not account for higher prevalence in women, but this is balanced by lower prevalence in younger people. From template 2, the algorithm combining hospital admissions and GP data identified 1597 women (MS5: 1327 not in UKMSR + 270 in UKMSR); the algorithm using the hospital database alone identified 1194 (MS1 [994+204]); both algorithms required recording of 2 episodes. More women were prescribed DMTs (6619) than were diagnosed with MS. These medicines had other, commoner indications (template 3), and using them without diagnostic codes to identify women with MS would over-report the prevalence of MS. However, information on the impact of medicines on pregnancy outcomes is relevant across diagnostic categories.

Data in both UKMSR and SAIL were incomplete for participants and prescribed medicines. Some 16% women in UKMSR did not have a diagnosis of MS in SAIL: diagnoses are self-reported and unverified (Middleton et al 2018), and it is conceivable that these participants had other neurological conditions.

Registration with the MS register is voluntary, and it appears that of the 1597 women with MS estimated by algorithm MS5 (template 2) only 403 women were on the register (template 1) (~25%); however, the exact proportion depended on the algorithm used to identify MS in SAIL (template 2). It is likely that UKMSR data in Wales are vulnerable to volunteer (Jordan et al 2013) and hence collider bias (Jordan et al 2022). Similarly, medicine (DMT) reporting was probably incomplete: we cannot be certain that volunteer respondents would complete data entry for these relatively complicated questions (Middleton et al 2018, appendix B). UKMSR identified a few medicine exposures not recorded in SAIL, which, as previously, we attribute to the absence of hospital prescribing from the SAIL databank (de Jonge et al 2015). UKMSR did not identify pregnancies by date of birth, and no matching could be attempted.

DMTs recorded

The proportion of patients potentially able to benefit from DMTs who are prescribed DMTs is lower in Wales than other countries in the UK, both in 2013 and 2016: 49% (Wales), 56% England, 57% Scotland, 77% Northern Ireland (MS Society 2016). DMTs are expensive (Table 3), and all health boards have long-standing budget deficits. DMTs are funded in Wales, with restrictions, but final decisions on treatment funding depend on 'appeal meetings' held *in camera*, where granting exceptions appears to depend on the eloquence of individual clinicians (Hughes & Dohey 2019a and b).

Most (~70%) women in SAIL and UKMSR did not have prescriptions for a DMT recorded: the literature indicates that ~50% would receive DMT (MS Society 2016). The prevalence of DMTs (disease modifying treatments) was low for several reasons: under-recording/ reporting (absence of hospital prescribing); possibly, therapeutic caution in women of childbearing age, who, at 15-55, may be at an early stage of disease, combined with uncertainty over adverse drug reactions and treatment costs; mismatch between study time-frame and drug marketing. Many of the DMTs investigated were not marketed in the earlier years of this study. Daclizumab, glatiramer, ofatumumab, siponimod, and ozanimod did not appear in either UKMSR or SAIL (Table 3). Siponimod and Ozanimod were too new to be identified in 2020. Cladribine and Ocrelizumab have also not been identified in any databanks in the Conception consortium, however, this needs further investigation. As for Glatiramer, Glatiramer acetate has been identified here and in other databanks but Glatiramer has not been recorded in any of the databanks in our consortium.

Algorithm selection is informed by this analysis.

- Using primary care plus admissions' data increased the numbers of women with MS identified (MS5 [the combination] identified 1597 women, whereas admissions data (MS1) gave 1198 women and primary care (MS3) gave 1052 women). Similarly, combining hospital episode statistics (HES) with GP data (CPRD) increased the prevalence of MS in women by 5.5% (MS5) (Mackenzie et al 2014). Using either alone missed at least 30% women on the UKMSR.
- Adding DMTs further increased the numbers identified. (MS8 & MS9).
- Reducing the number of events / prescriptions in the algorithms increased the numbers identified, at the risk of increasing the false positive rate. False positives could be attributed to mis-diagnoses by clinicians or clinical suspicions being recorded as diagnoses or, more rarely, data entry errors. MS is a clinical diagnosis, and many suspected cases prove to be other conditions e.g. Lyme disease, brucellosis, B12

deficiency, other infections or inflammatory conditions, some of which are self-remitting, as is MS in many cases. Swedish investigators found optimal sensitivity and specificity were obtained when using 3 visits to clinics or hospitals (Teljas et al 2021).

- Using only DMTs (MS7) identified many fewer women on the UKMSR than other algorithms. Medicines with several indications identified many (~1,000) women without MS.

UKMSR holds data on very few pregnant women: between 1998 and 2020 we identified <65 whilst the woman was on the register (and completing questionnaires either quarterly or every 6 months, above) and <300 with previous pregnancies. In contrast, SAIL holds data on >1,000 pregnancies, 1287 after diagnosis. Some of this discrepancy can be attributed to the extended timeframe of SAIL; during earlier periods several of the medicines of interest were unavailable, reducing the benefits of using SAIL, but still providing ten times more pregnancies. In addition, >2,500 pregnancies exposed to DMTs, regardless of indications, are available for analysis.

Population data compared with disease registers

Both data collection strategies are important sources of information on long-term conditions. Volunteer registers' loss of fidelity to the real-world population, through selection and collider bias, may be balanced by more detailed information; for example, registers are likely to be better placed to collect accurate data on paternity, consanguinity, and family history than electronic health records (Richardson et al 2023). However, they are unlikely to offer sufficient follow up to collect data on the children's education outcomes that determine their life chances. It is uncertain which form of data collection gives more accurate information on alcohol or substance misuse: population databases accurately document referrals, but have little information on casual use, although such issues are not always accurately reported to fieldworkers or in questionnaires. Smoking is reported more frequently to the UKMSR than to clinicians (15% vs. 11% n=265) (Rogers et al 2022). Adherence to therapeutic regimens, with exact start and end dates, and purchased medicines may be more accurately reported in questionnaires than from prescribing or dispensing records, particularly where hospital prescribing data are unavailable. However, none of this information was available to us in UKMSR. In this study, the electronic database reported ten times more pregnancies. Generally, manufacturers' medicine-related pregnancy registers capture insufficient data on pregnancy, infant follow-up, and breastfeeding: median (interquartile range) enrolment is reported as 36 (5-258) pregnancies and 12 (2-119) infants (Bird et al 2018). Patient safety researchers are, therefore, examining population databases; however, data quality and validity are not always completely evaluated (Rawson et al 2018, Pacurariu et al 2018), and many have no data on substance misuse, breastfeeding, neurodevelopment and education (Coathup et al 2020, Roque Pereira et al 2022, Jordan et al 2022, 2023).

We found the UKMSR unsuitable for study of pregnancy or breastfeeding:

- The low number of recorded pregnancies in UKMSR (<65,2011-2020) indicates this is a suboptimal source of information on pregnancy outcomes. Most adverse perinatal outcomes affect <5% of infants (Supplementary Table 3); therefore, reporting results of any investigation would generate wide confidence intervals and contravene governance restrictions on reporting numbers <5.
- The mean age of women using UKMSR is >53, militating against its use to explore pregnancy outcomes.
- Many women had been pregnant before contributing data to UKMSR, and these outcomes were not included in the register.
- A low proportion of pregnant women (<10%) voluntarily participated in this disease register.
- Volunteers rarely provided data on their medicines or timing of administration.
- Prescribing information in UKMSR is too sparse to address medication safety issues.
- The Wales population databank can follow children to age 16 and obtain education outcome data, but there is no comparable structure in UKMSR.
- There was no mention of breastfeeding.

Complex questions on medicines in pregnancy and lactation are better explored in the SAIL population databank than the UKMSR online. However, the absence of hospital prescribing detracts from SAIL, and only one hospital in Wales contributes data to UKMSR. This sub-study did not explore other registers or registers devoted to collecting data on pregnancy.

Strengths and Limitations of this study

- This was a single-centre study, based in a small European country, with a relatively low use of DMTs; as such it may not be representative of larger, wealthier European nations.
- Women who joined the UKMSR self-identified with MS. It is possible that their primary care teams were unaware of their diagnoses and that they had never been admitted to hospital with MS. There is a possibility that there were alternative diagnoses in some cases.
- The recording of pregnancies in the UKMSR was unexpectedly low (<65). Therefore, our governance regulations on low numbers prohibited reporting of adverse perinatal outcomes that affect no more than 3% of infants.
- Exploration of covariates, such as socio-economic status and obesity was not within scope, but UKMSR held little information on these. UKMSR holds information on the Expanded Disability Status Score, but such measures are rarely recorded in GP data.
- Mother-child linkage for long-term follow-up was not within scope, so we are unable to offer long-term data on pregnancy outcomes. However, UKMSR did not hold the relevant variables.
- The medicines under investigation have several indications, but indications are not always recorded in Wales' primary care database. Some medicines listed in the Conception algorithm are not currently indicated for MS, and some were too new to market to be prescribed (Template 3). Several medicines prescribable for MS in the UK were not included in the algorithms e.g. fampridine, ponesimod. However, these findings offer guidance on the choice of algorithm for identification of MS in healthcare databases.

- The absence of hospital prescribing data detracts from this work.
- Where medicines are only available for intravenous administration or single doses are prescribed in secondary care, primary care recording may be incomplete. For medicines administered orally or by sc or im injection, doses administered in hospital may not appear in SAIL; however, these medicines are typically continued by primary care physicians, and are recorded.
- Our estimate of the prevalence of MS in SAIL was based on a single record. This was the estimate closest to the calculated population prevalence.
- We have based our population MS prevalence calculation on estimates for Wales 1990-2010 (Mackenzie et al 2014, Balbuena et al 2016). Higher prevalence was reported for women across the UK (289/100,000), with the highest prevalence in women 50-59 (639/100,000), many of whom were outside the age range for this study, and lower prevalence for women 20-29 (58/100,000). MS prevalence is lower in Wales than elsewhere in the UK, and declined 1990 to 2010 (Mackenzie et al 2014). The figure of 289/100,000 suggests that, from a population of 917,138, we should expect ~2650 women to be identified with MS, rather than 1540. In our view, the prevalence of 289/100,000 does not account for the younger age of our cohort. However, it is possible that the current algorithms provided by Conception may not identify all women with MS. Many DMTs listed are not prescribed exclusively for MS, and some are not indicated for MS, but their impact on pregnancy outcomes warrants investigation.
- Where single events are accepted, coding or diagnostic errors are possible.

Conclusion

Any case ascertainment algorithm needs both primary care & hospital diagnostic data. Algorithms for DMTs with multiple indications are unlikely to identify only cases of any one condition (Table 3). Excluding all alternative indications from any dataset will be time-consuming and probably incomplete.

Our aim was to draw broad comparisons between a recruited volunteer cohort and a whole-population cohort based on routine data. The volunteer cohort from UKMSR was too small to be representative of the national population or provide useful information on the safety of medicines in pregnancy. It did, however, capture some prescribing that was not recorded in the routine data, due to the absence of hospital prescribing data. Where resources for pharmacovigilance are limited, national, whole-population databanks should be prioritised over recruited volunteer cohorts, as they are more likely to capture a useful volume of data, free of selection bias, within a realistic timeframe with opportunity for follow up of children to age 16 for health and education outcomes. UKMSR currently contributes little to pregnancy and breastfeeding studies. However, UKMSR are currently recruiting to a study on pregnancy, organised by Queen Mary's College, Barts and the London, University of London.

https://ukmsregister.org/Documents/Studies/Pregnancy/patient_information_sheet_long_v2_1606.pdf. At the time of writing, around 200 women have been recruited.

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Ethics and governance

Ethical approval was granted by the MS society, letter of 23.1.21, and the SAIL information governance team, within the framework of the Conception project. Following approval, the MS data were provisioned to the project on the 23.06.21. UKMSR data collection is approved by South West – Central Bristol Research Ethics Committee (16/SW/0194), an independent NHS Research Ethics Committee <https://ukmsregister.org/Account/Register>

Contributions

Swansea University linked, extracted and analysed the data (Ieuan Scanlon, Daniel Thayer) and wrote the report (Sue Jordan)

Faculty of Medicine, Health and Life Science, Swansea University, Swansea, Wales, United Kingdom (UK)

St. George's, London provided the algorithms and list of medicines to be investigated (Joan Morris, Matt Pryce) Details are provided in template 3.

Data acquisition and review: Rod Middleton MS Society, Faculty of Medicine, Health and Life Science, Swansea University, Swansea, Wales, United Kingdom (UK)

Review: David Tucker, Public Health Wales, Wales, United Kingdom (UK)

Repository for primary data

Data are held in SAIL. All relevant data are available in this report.

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Supplementary Table 1 : Algorithms in SAIL 1998-2009 / 2010-2020

Here we calculated the number of women as per the event/ visit occurred per person between the year 1998-2009 and 2010-2020, rather than considering initially diagnosed date, so some women present in 1998 to 2009 can also be included in 2010 to 2020.

The count in 1998 to 2020 period (above) gives the unique number as it is considered as a single duration, however the period 1998 to 2009 and 2010 to 2020 cannot be added to get 1998 to 2020 as it depends on each individual events.

	Number of Women aged 15-55: 1998 - 2009		
	In UKMSR with pre 2010 data and in SAIL with MS diagnoses pre 2010	In UKMSR with pre 2010 data and in SAIL but with no MS diagnoses pre 2010	Not in UKMSR pre 2010, but in SAIL with MS diagnoses pre 2010
MS1	73	330	483
MS2	57	346	391
MS3	114	289	502
MS4	74	329	327
MS5	133	270	710
MS6	101	302	535
MS7	<5	<400	1376
MS8	163	240	2436
MS9	135	268	2356
MS10	104	299	2182
	Number of Women aged 15-55: 2010-2020		
	In UKMSR post 2010 and in SAIL with MS diagnoses post 2010	In UKMSR post 2010 and in SAIL but with no MS diagnoses post 2010	Not in UKMSR post 2010, but in SAIL with MS diagnoses post 2010
MS1	176	227	772
MS2	132	271	544
MS3	119	284	473
MS4	66	337	254
MS5	222	181	997
MS6	163	240	690
MS7	<5	<400	2624
MS8	312	91	4479
MS9	252	151	4556
MS10	206	197	4289

Supplementary Table 2 : Women 15-55 in UKMSR and SAIL

Women 15-55 with a pregnancy in the databases since 1998-2020

		In PEDW		
		Yes	No	Total
In MS register	Yes	187	40	227
	No	846	2746	3592
Total		1033	2786	

Women 15-55 with a pregnancy in the databases since 1998-2020

		In GP data with ATCs listed		
		Yes	No	Total
In MS register	Yes	70	157	227
	No	2254	1038	3592
Total		2624	1195	

Women 15-55 with a pregnancy in the databases since 1998-2020

		In GP data with MS diagnosis		
		Yes	No	Total
In MS register	Yes	207	20	227
	No	933	2659	3592
Total		1140	2679	

Women 15-55 with a pregnancy in the databases 2011-2020 (start of MS register)

		In PEDW		
		Yes	No	Total
In MS register	Yes	50	<15	<65
	No	329	972	1301
Total		379	<987	

Women 15-55 with a pregnancy in the databases 2011-2020 (start of MS register)

		In GP data with ATCs listed		
		Yes	no	Total
In MS register	Yes	<25	42	<65
	No	928	373	1301
Total		<953	415	

Women 15-55 with a pregnancy in the databases 2011-2020 (start of MS register)

		In GP data with MS diagnosis		
		Yes	no	Total
In MS register	Yes	60	<5	<65
	No	350	951	1301
Total		410	<956	

Supplementary Table 3 : Prevalence of adverse pregnancy and neonatal outcomes in Wales

Data for Wales has been used, where available. For some parameters, the nearest approximation is data for 'England and Wales'. Where this is unavailable, data has been sought from publications.

Outcome	Pregnancies included	Prevalence	Source / reference
Maternal death	All pregnancies	8.8/100,000 UK during & 6 weeks after birth 2017-19	Knight M, Bunch K, Tuffnell D, Patel R, Shakespeare J, Kotnis R, Kenyon S, Kurinczuk JJ (Eds.) on behalf of MBRRACE-UK. Saving Lives, Improving Mothers' Care - Lessons learned to inform maternity care from the UK and Ireland Confidential Enquiries into Maternal Deaths and Morbidity 2017-19. Oxford: National Perinatal Epidemiology Unit, University of Oxford 2021. https://www.npeu.ox.ac.uk/assets/downloads/mbrrace-uk/reports/maternal-report-2021/MBRRACE-UK_Maternal_Report_2021_-_FINAL_-_WEB_VERSION.pdf
Spontaneous abortion	All pregnancies	Unknown 20-25%	
Termination of Pregnancy for Foetal Anomaly (TOPFA)	All pregnancies	~1 to 250 all conceptions ~1 to 200 live births England & Wales	3,370 of 214,256 terminations (1.6%) 2021 + 624,828 live births (0.4% or 3379/839064) SB not accounted or 0.54% - 3379/624,828 live births https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/birthsdeathsandmarriages/livebirths/bulletins/birthsummarytablesenglandandwales/2021#:~:text=In%202021%2C%20there%20were%20624%2C828,trend%20of%20decreasing%20live%20births. https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/abortion-statistics-for-england-and-wales-2021/abortion-statistics-england-and-wales-2021
Caesarean section	All pregnancies	28.3% Wales 2019	Europeristat 2022 EUROPEAN PERINATAL HEALTH REPORT Core indicators of the health and care of pregnant women and babies in Europe from 2015 to 2019 Euro-Peristat Fact sheets 2022 for upload.pdf (europeristat.com) Also: NHS Maternity Statistics, England - 2021-22 - NHS Digital https://digital.nhs.uk/data-and-information/publications/statistical/nhs-maternity-statistics gives 35% section rate
Pre-term birth	Live births only	7% Wales 2019	Europeristat 2022 EUROPEAN PERINATAL HEALTH REPORT Core indicators of the health and care of pregnant women and babies in Europe from 2015 to 2019 Euro-Peristat Fact sheets 2022 for upload.pdf (europeristat.com)
Stillbirth	Pregnancies at least 24 weeks of gestational age	119/28,994 (0.41%) Wales 2019	Europeristat 2022 EUROPEAN PERINATAL HEALTH REPORT Core indicators of the health and care of pregnant women and babies in Europe from 2015 to 2019 Euro-Peristat Fact sheets 2022 for upload.pdf (europeristat.com)
Neonatal death	Live births only	≥22 weeks 0.27% to 27 days, 0.21% to 7 days ≥24 weeks 0.14% England & Wales 2019	Europeristat 2022 EUROPEAN PERINATAL HEALTH REPORT Core indicators of the health and care of pregnant women and babies in Europe from 2015 to 2019 Euro-Peristat Fact sheets 2022 for upload.pdf (europeristat.com)
Low birth weight	Live births only	<2500g 7.1% 2019 England and Wales	Europeristat 2022 EUROPEAN PERINATAL HEALTH REPORT Core indicators of the health and care of pregnant women and babies in Europe from 2015 to 2019 Euro-Peristat Fact sheets 2022 for upload.pdf (europeristat.com)
Small-for-gestational age	Live births only	<10 th centile 8-10% Wales SAIL cohort	Jordan S, Davies GI, Thayer DS, Tucker D, Humphreys I (2019) Antidepressant prescriptions, discontinuation, depression

(SGA)/ Intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR)		2000-10	and perinatal outcomes, including breastfeeding: A population cohort analysis. PLOS ONE 14(11): e0225133. https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0225133
Low Apgar score (5- minute)	Live births only	1.4-1.9% Apgar <7 at 5 minutes 2016- 9 0.1% Apgar 0-3 at 5 minutes - Denmark 1978-2000	Statistics Wales 2022 Maternity and Birth Statistics 2021 https://gov.wales/maternity-and-birth-statistics-2021-html Ladelund, AK, Bruun, FJ, Slavensky, JA, Ladelund, S, Kesmodel, US. Association of Apgar score at 5 minutes with academic performance and intelligence in youth: A cohort study. <i>Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand.</i> 2022; 101: 303– 312. doi: 10.1111/aogs.14320
Major congenital anomalies	Live births only	3.15% Wales SAIL cohort 2000-10, including TOPFAs, excluding chromosomal anomalies. CARIS gives 5% 1998-2020 all Wales all births	Jordan S, Morris JK, Davies GI, Tucker D, Thayer DS, Luteijn JM, Morgan M, Garne E, Hansen AV, Klungsøyr K, Engeland A, Boyle B, Dolk H (2016) Selective Serotonin Reuptake Inhibitor (SSRI) antidepressants in Pregnancy and Congenital Anomalies: analysis of linked databases in Wales, Norway and Funen, Denmark. <i>Plos One</i> 11(12): e0165122. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0165122 CARIS 2021 Annual review and data tables. https://phw.nhs.wales/services-and-teams/caris/annual-review-data-tables/